

Khmilnik's articles

(for articles in DNA magazine, see separate catalogue)

Num	Title	Publisher:	Link	DNA:	Link	Acad:	Link	Authors
582	Mass forces' dependence on the speed and mathematical models of some natural phenomena	Canadian Journal of Pure and Applied Sciences		8104300	https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118230104.ch104	104118230	https://www.cjpas.org/doi/10.1002/9781118230104.ch104	S. Khmelnik
581	THE NATURE OF THE CORIOLIS FORCE AND FLYBY ANOMALY	Canadian Journal of Pure and Applied Sciences,		8104272	https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118083104.ch104	104118083	https://www.cjpas.org/doi/10.1002/9781118083104.ch104	S. Khmelnik
578	A REVIEW ON THE BOOK BY KHMELNIK: NAVIER-STOKES EQUATIONS ON THE EXISTENCE AND THE SEARCH METHOD FOR GLOBAL SOLUTIONS	Canadian Journal of Pure and Applied Sciences	https://www.cjpas.org/doi/10.1002/9781118083104.ch104	5670405	https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118083104.ch104			Zakharenko Aleksy Anatolievich
576ac	New equations for the spinning top	Canadian Journal of Pure and Applied Sciences	https://www.cjpas.org/doi/10.1002/9781118083104.ch104	8197236	https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118083104.ch104			S. Khmelnik
575c	Fix of electrodynamics	Canadian Journal of Pure and Applied Sciences	https://www.cjpas.org/doi/10.1002/9781118083104.ch104	8197218	https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118083104.ch104			S. Khmelnik
538	SPACE FLIGHTS AND ELECTROMAGNETIC FIELD MOMENTUM	Canadian Journal of Pure and Applied Sciences		3911582	https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118083104.ch104	43455986	https://www.cjpas.org/doi/10.1002/9781118083104.ch104	S. Khmelnik
525e	Electromagnetic Keeper of Energy and Information	Canadian Journal of Pure and Applied Sciences	http://www.cjpas.org/doi/10.1002/9781118083104.ch104	3518396	https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118083104.ch104	40756197	https://www.cjpas.org/doi/10.1002/9781118083104.ch104	S. Khmelnik
518ec	Gravity Antenna	Canadian Journal of Pure and Applied Sciences	http://www.cjpas.org/doi/10.1002/9781118083104.ch104	2542263	https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118083104.ch104	37639744	https://www.cjpas.org/doi/10.1002/9781118083104.ch104	S. Khmelnik
509ac	A Method and System for Braking of Flying Objects	Canadian Journal of Pure and Applied Sciences	http://www.cjpas.org/doi/10.1002/9781118083104.ch104	1305195	https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118083104.ch104	37686231	https://www.cjpas.org/doi/10.1002/9781118083104.ch104	S. Khmelnik
570	Mas sobre el refinamiento experimental de las ecuaciones de gravedad de Maxwell	Journalusco	https://journalusco.com/doi/10.25054/90371705	yes	10.25054/90371705	90371705	https://www.cjpas.org/doi/10.1002/9781118083104.ch104	S. Khmelnik, I.H. Tafur Perdomo

569	Four forces in mechanics	Academia Letters			yes	https://doi.org/10.21467/ajl.80854442	80854442	https://www.academia.edu/80854442	S. Khmelnik
532	To the Rationale for Homeopathy	Determinations in Nanomedicine		https://crim.iosrjournals.org			42867143	https://www.iosrjournals.org	S. Khmelnik
526	Permanent magnets in nanostructures and organisms				3360131	https://doi.org/10.21467/ajl.3360131	40756266	https://www.academia.edu/40756266	S. Khmelnik
523e	Levitation of rotating discs	IOSR Journal of Applied Physics		http://www.iosrjournals.org	3533766	https://doi.org/10.21467/ajl.3533766	41710105	https://www.iosrjournals.org	S. Khmelnik
520	The spiral structure of electromagnetic waves and of stationary electromagnetic field	IOSR Journal of Applied Physics		http://www.iosrjournals.org	3533718	https://doi.org/10.21467/ajl.3533718	41618824	https://www.iosrjournals.org	S. Khmelnik
521	Nanoengineering and Maxwell's Equations	Determinations in Nanomedicine		https://crim.iosrjournals.org	3533739	https://doi.org/10.21467/ajl.3533739			S. Khmelnik
530	About the Interaction of Nanoparticles	Determinations in Nanomedicine		https://crim.iosrjournals.org	3660667	https://doi.org/10.21467/ajl.3660667			S. Khmelnik
517e	A new approach to antenna design	Scholar Journal of Applied Sciences and Research		https://www.sjar.in	2542268	https://doi.org/10.21467/ajl.2542268	37681294	https://www.sjar.in	S. Khmelnik
235.3	Computer Arithmetic of Numbers, Vectors, Figures and Functions. Algorithms and Hardware	iJournals: International Journal of Software & Hardware Research in Engineering		https://ijournal.org	3920213	https://doi.org/10.21467/ajl.3920213	43463712	https://www.ijournal.org	S. Khmelnik
298e	Method and algorithm for calculation of turbulent flows	London Journal of Research in Science			2542020	https://doi.org/10.21467/ajl.2542020	40251345	https://www.ljrs.in	S. Khmelnik
512ev	New Solution of Maxwell's Equations for Spherical Wave	ViXra	1801.0348	http://vixra.org	1306967	https://doi.org/10.21467/ajl.1306967			S. Khmelnik
511e	Solution of Maxwell's Equations for a Capacitor with Alternating Voltage	ViXra	1710.0204	http://vixra.org					S. Khmelnik
510e	More About the Inconsistency Solution of the Maxwell Equations	ViXra	1709.0361	http://vixra.org					S. Khmelnik
507ve	Why Don't Clouds Fall?	ViXra	1701.0605	http://vixra.org			31280628	https://www.vixra.org	S. Khmelnik
498e	The Equation of Whirlpool	ViXra	1506.0157	http://vixra.org					S. Khmelnik

492a	The Electromagnetic Wave in Alternating Current Wire	ViXra	1603.0260	http://vixra					S. Khmelnik
479ve	Mathematical Model of Dust Whirl	ViXra	1505.0087	http://vixra			28917721	https://wv	S. Khmelnik
474ve	More About the Nature of the Earth's Magnetism	ViXra	1605.0118	http://vixra					S. Khmelnik
473ve	The Electromagnetic Wave in a Spherical Capacitor and the Nature of Earth	ViXra	1604.0371	http://vixra					S. Khmelnik
472ve	The Electromagnetic Wave in a Charged Capacitor	ViXra	1604.0374	http://vixra					S. Khmelnik
471ve	The Electromagnetic Wave in the Dielectric and Magnetic Circuit of Alternating Current	ViXra	1604.0151	http://vixra					S. Khmelnik
470ve	Structure of Constant Current	ViXra	1504.0170	http://vixra			28917730	https://wv	S. Khmelnik
468ve	Mathematical Model of Ball Lightning	ViXra	1503.0065	http://vixra					S. Khmelnik
464ve	The Second Solution of Maxwell's Equations	ViXra	1602.0084	http://vixra					S. Khmelnik
463ve	The Experiment Confirming the Existence of the Fourth Electromagnetic Induction	ViXra	1601.0305	http://vixra					S. Khmelnik
461	Experiment for the proof of Newton's Third Law Violation in Unipolar Motor	ViXra	1501.0102	http://vixra					S. Khmelnik
460a	The Second Structure of Constant Current	ViXra	1511.0231	http://vixra					S. Khmelnik
411ve	A Source of Conservative Forces do Work on a Closed Trajectory	ViXra	1507.0146	http://vixra					S. Khmelnik
323ve	Second Mathematical Model of Ball Lightning	ViXra	1605.0279	http://vixra					S. Khmelnik
312ve	Unusual Fountain and Gravitomagnetism	ViXra	1509.0042	http://vixra					S. Khmelnik
288a	Electromagnetic Energy Flow in the Wire and Milroy Engine	ViXra	1511.0130	http://vixra					S. Khmelnik

251.v2	Principle Extremum of full Action in	ViXra	1401.0209	http://vixra					S. Khmelnik
458a	The Fourth Electromagnetic Induction	ViXra	1412.0224	http://vixra			28917728	https://www	S. Khmelnik
251.e	Principle Extremum of full Action in Electrodynamics	ViXra	1401.0209	http://vixra					S. Khmelnik
251.e	Principle extremum of full action	European researcher		http://www					S. Khmelnik
199	Arithmetic Unit for Complex Number Processing	Researchgate		https://www					<u>S. Khmelnik,</u> <u>S. Selyutin,</u> <u>A. Viduetsky,</u> <u>I. Doubson</u>
251	Study on Principle Extremum of Full	Researchgate		https://www					S. Khmelnik
569	Four forces in mechanics	Researchgate		https://www					S. Khmelnik
558	The open letter to the Clay Mathematics Institute (CMI) «On the sixth problem of millennium»	Researchgate		https://www	DOI: 10.13140 /RG. 2.2.22610.2 7844	https://www	90364791	https://www	S. Khmelnik
529e	Adjustable Rotoverter (Fuel-free Energy Generator)				3520129	https://doi	40756159	https://www	S. Khmelnik
522	An engine for spacecraft. Proposal for patenting application.				2563858	https://doi	38335627	https://www	S. Khmelnik
007c	Computer for operations with Functions	Wikipedia		https://en.v					S. Khmelnik